

hydrochloric acid (10%) and water and dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 . The solvent was removed and the residue on distillation under reduced pressure afforded the ester. The purity of the product was checked through TLC. IR: 3400 ($-\text{NH}$), 1685 ($-\text{C}=\text{O}$ group), 1550 (secondary amine), 980 (trans double bond in conjugation with carbonyl group) cm^{-1} .

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Synthesis and Antibacterial Activity of Thiazolyl Guanidines

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A number of biguanides¹ and guanidines have been reported to exhibit antitubercular² and antimalarial³ activities. Bhargava et al⁴⁻⁷ have shown that benzothiazolyl guanidines are antibacterials, antituberculars and CNS depressants. Besides such compounds are more active against Gram-positive bacteria than Gram-negative ones^{8,9}.

In the present communication, the author has synthesised some new *N*-aryl-*N'*-2-(4-*p*-methylphenyl)-thiazolyl-*N''*-alkyl (or H) guanidines and screened for their antibacterial activities.

Experimental

N-Aryl-*N'*-2-(4-*p*-methylphenyl)-thiazolyl thiocarbamides were prepared by the reaction of 2-amino-4-*p*-methylphenyl thiazole and phenyl isothiocyanate or *p*-methoxyphenyl isothiocyanate in dry benzene.

N-Phenyl-*N'*-2-(4-*p*-methylphenyl)-thiazolyl-*N''*-methyl guanidine (2):

A mixture of *N*-phenyl-*N'*-2-(4-*p*-methylphenyl)-thiazolyl thiocarbamide (1.6 g), yellow lead oxide (2.5 g) and 33% aqueous methylamine solution (3.0 ml) in 20 ml of ethanol was heated in a steel-autoclave on a water-bath for about three hours with

occasional shaking. The autoclave was opened carefully and the reaction mixture was filtered. The black residue was further extracted with four 10-ml portions of ethanol and filtered hot. The combined filtrate was concentrated and the product was recrystallised from dilute ethanol into yellow coloured crystals.

Similarly, other *N*-phenyl-*N'*-2-(4-*p*-methylphenyl)-thiazolyl-*N''*-alkyl (or H) guanidines were prepared using different alkyl amines or ammonia and are listed in Table 1.

N-*p*-Methoxyphenyl-*N'*-2-(4-*p*-methylphenyl)-thiazolyl-*N''*-alkyl (or H) guanidines:

These guanidines were prepared as described above using *N*-*p*-methoxyphenyl-*N'*-2-(4-*p*-methylphenyl)-thiazolyl thiocarbamide and different alkyl amines or ammonia and listed in Table 1.

TABLE 1—*N*-ARYL-*N'*-2-(4-*p*-METHYLPHENYL)-THIAZOLYL-*N''*-ALKYL (OR H) GUANIDINES

Sl. No.	Alkyl group R'	Molecular formula	Yield (%)	M.P. (°C)
R=H				
1.	H	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_4\text{S}$	64	150
2.	Methyl	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_4\text{S}$	78	159
3.	Ethyl	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_4\text{S}$	68	128
4.	<i>n</i> -Propyl	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_4\text{S}$	72	93
5.	<i>n</i> -Butyl	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_4\text{S}$	58	100
6.	<i>iso</i> -Butyl	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_4\text{S}$	85	76
R= <i>p</i> -Methoxy				
7.	H	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_4\text{OS}$	54	171
8.	Methyl	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_4\text{OS}$	52	154
9.	Ethyl	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_4\text{OS}$	73	103
10.	<i>n</i> -Propyl	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_4\text{OS}$	72	105
11.	<i>iso</i> -Propyl	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_4\text{OS}$	68	121
12.	<i>n</i> -Butyl	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_4\text{OS}$	75	100
13.	<i>iso</i> -Butyl	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_4\text{OS}$	81	112

(a) All the melting points are uncorrected.

(b) All the compounds were analysed for C, H, N and S; the observed values were within a range of $\pm 0.35\%$ of the calculated values.

(c) IR and PMR spectral data were in well agreement with the synthesised compounds.

Screening Results :

The results of the antibacterial screening of the seven synthesised compounds are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—*N*-ARYL-*N'*-2-(4-METHYLPHENYL)-THIAZOLYL-*N''*-ALKYL (OR H) GUANIDINES

Sl. No.	Alkyl group	(Concentration—1000 ppm)	
		Bacteria	
		<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
Aryl group=Phenyl			
1.	H	+	+
2.	Ethyl	+	+
3.	<i>n</i> -Butyl	-	+
Aryl group= <i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl			
4.	H	-	+
5.	Methyl	+	+
6.	Ethyl	-	+
7.	<i>n</i> -Propyl	+	+

(+) Growth ; (-) No growth.

The test organisms were *B. subtilis*, a bacteria from Gram-positive group and *E. coli*, a bacteria from Gram-negative group and the concentration used was 1000 ppm. From the results it can be inferred that the thiazolyl guanidines are more active against Gram-positive bacteria than the Gram-negative one.

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Search for New Hypoglycemic Agents-Part IV N¹-(Arylideneamino)-N³-(Arylsulphonamido) Guanidines

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A series of N¹-(arylideneamino)-N³-(arylsulphonamido)-guanidines has been synthesised. Three of these compounds when screened on rats at an oral dose of 250 mg/kg reduced the blood sugar up to 9%.

It has been reported that several guanidines¹⁻⁴ possess significant hypoglycemic activity. Some arylsulphonamides⁵⁻⁷ are also known to exhibit marked antidiabetic property. It seemed, therefore, of interest to synthesise the title compounds with the object to ascertain whether the presence of arylsulphonamido moiety in guanidines could augment their hypoglycemic potency.

N¹-(Arylidene) thiosemicarbazide was refluxed with methyl iodide in ethanol for 2 hr. to give the hydroiodide of N¹-(arylidene)-S-methyl thiosemicarbazide. The latter was treated with aqueous 2N-Na₂CO₃ solution to yield N¹-(arylidene)-S-methyl thiosemicarbazide which on being refluxed with various aryl sulphonyl hydrazines in ethanol for 48 hr furnished N¹-(arylideneamino)-N³-(arylsulphonamido) guanidines.

Experimental

Melting points are not corrected. I. R. spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer 577 in KBr pellets.

N¹-(Arylidene) thiosemicarbazides : were prepared according to the method of Jack et al⁸.

N¹-(Arylidene)-S-methyl thiosemicarbazides :

A mixture of N¹-(arylidene) thiosemicarbazide (.05 mole) and methyl iodide (.05 mole) in ethanol (100 ml) was refluxed for 4 hr. The reaction mixture was poured into ice cold water and filtered. The filtrate consisting of the HI-salt of N¹-(arylidene)-S-methyl thiosemicarbazide was neutralized with aqueous 2N-Na₂CO₃ solution to give the precipitate of N¹-(arylidene)-S-methyl thiosemicarbazide which was recrystallized from ethanol.

The properties and analytical data of the compounds thus obtained are summarized in Table 1.

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